

MECHANISM OF VACUUM HOT PRESSING OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

V.V. Bhanu Prasad*, B.V.R. Bhat*, A.C. Rao*, V.K.Varma*,
Y.R. Mahajan* and P. Ramakrishnan**

* Defence Metallurgical Research Laboratory, Hyderabad, India 500 058.

** Department of Metallurgy, IIT, Bombay, India 400 074.

ABSTRACT

Effect of vacuum hot pressing pressure and temperature on the compaction behaviour of Al-4.0 Cu-1.5 Mg alloy powder containing different volume fractions of silicon carbide particulates of different particle sizes was investigated. Solid state compaction followed by semi-solid state compaction was used to make the material. The microstructures were analysed and based on preliminary work a mechanism of densification is proposed involving infiltration of liquid metal rich in alloying elements into the capillaries between the SiC_p present in the necklace region. The processing temperature and pressure depend on the volume fraction and particle size of the reinforcement.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminium matrix composites containing discontinuous ceramic reinforcement have been the subject of intensive investigation around the world due to their attractive properties such as high specific stiffness, improved strength, good dimensional stability, better wear resistance and superior high temperature strength [1,2]. Silicon carbide is the most proven reinforcement for aluminium base MMCs [3,4]. Processing of these composites is the crucial step in mastering the technology of these materials. Out of the numerous fabrication techniques available for producing MMCs with discontinuous reinforcements [5-7], two routes are very common, namely liquid metallurgy approach [5] and the powder metallurgy approach [6]. The powder metallurgy method involves atomization of matrix Al powders, deagglomeration of reinforcement powder to remove the static surface charges, blending of matrix and reinforcement powders in the required proportion, degassing of blended powders, cold compaction of powders and finally hot compaction. Several hot compaction techniques such as hot isostatic pressing (HIP), hot forging or hot rolling of canned MMC powder/compact, vacuum hot pressing are available for hot consolidation of powders. Out of them vacuum hot pressing is the most suitable for hot consolidation of powders.

Vacuum hot pressing involves heating of the powders/CIP'ed compacts placed in a die under vacuum to the required temperature and then pressing the porous mass into a fully dense compact. VHP process for Al/SiC MMCs was developed [8] by optimising the temperature and pressure cycle using a GCA hot press where the maximum load that could be applied is limited to 26 MPa. Consolidation of MMC powders was carried out at various temperatures in between

480 - 625 °C. It was found that pre-consolidation prior to hot pressing and semi-solid pressing are essential to achieve the high density compacts of MMCs. The main objective of vacuum hot pressing is to achieve 100% theoretical density without forming intermetallic precipitates, divorced eutectic and also without causing agglomeration of SiC. The temperature of final pressing should be above the solidus to have enough liquid phase to achieve full density but should not be so high as to cause coarse intermetallic precipitate formation or to make the melt too fluid to cause leakage through gaps. Vacuum hot pressing route was also used by AEA Technology, U.K., for the production of MMCs [9].

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The materials used in the investigation were Al - 4.0 Cu - 1.5 Mg atomised aluminium powders (-200#) as the matrix and SiC particles (1.9 µm and 14 µm) as reinforcements. The process adopted for making the MMCs are shown in the flow chart given in Fig. 1. The aluminium powder and the SiC particles (0 vol.% , 15 vol.% and 30 vol.%) were dry blended in a planetary mixer. The dry blended powders were degassed at 480 °C for 6 hours to remove absorbed and adsorbed moisture and the degassed powders were cold isostatically pressed into compacts. The green compacts were machined to the die size (75 mm dia X 200 mm height) and hot compacted in two stages. First stage of compaction involves heating the green compacts to 500 °C and after complete degassing, pressing the compact to the maximum possible density. In the second stage, keeping the pressure constant at 115 MPa, the temperature of the material was gradually increased till the billet attains full density. It is essential to process this material at temperatures above solidus to achieve full density. Hence two stage hot compaction was adopted to produce full density MMC billets. Load, temperature, compaction data was obtained from all the experiments at predetermined time intervals while compaction is going on. Microstructural studies were carried out by scanning electron microscope and electron probe microanalyser.

Fig.1. Process flow chart for making MMCs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the first stage, composite densification is studied as a function of compaction load at 500 °C which is below solidus temperature. First stage compaction curves are drawn for compaction of the Al alloy, Al alloy / 15 vol.% SiC_p (1.9 μm), Al alloy / 15 vol.% SiC_p (14 μm) and Al alloy / 30 vol.% SiC_p (1.9 μm) in Fig. 2. In the second stage, further compact

Fig.2. I stage compaction curves.

Fig.3. II stage compaction curves.

densification is studied as a function of hot pressing temperature, at a constant pressure of 115 MPa. The second stage compacting curves for all the above mentioned materials are shown in Fig. 3. Unreinforced sample could be hot pressed to full density below solidus (i.e., 480-500 °C). In case of lower volume fraction of SiC (i.e., 15 vol.%) the compaction behaviour is similar up to 91 - 92% densification irrespective of reinforcement particle size. Thereafter it depends strongly on particle size, whereas in case of higher volume fraction (i.e., 30 vol.%) of SiC composites, the compaction behaviour is a weak function of compaction pressure. At 500 °C the composite densification, as a result of 115 MPa compacting pressure, varies in between 90 -99% depending upon reinforcement particle size and volume fraction. Further densification over and above these values has to take place by liquid metal infiltration.

Metallographic samples from the VHP billets were mounted and polished using conventional metallographic procedures. Fig.4. shows the microstructure of unreinforced matrix material and composite containing 15 vol.% SiC_p (1.9 μm), 15 vol.% SiC_p (14 μm) and 30 vol.% SiC_p (1.9 μm) in as-VHP condition. From these microstructures, the potential of the PM process adopted for making this material is demonstrated in terms of uniform distribution of SiC_p and absence of porosity. The Al alloy / 30 vol.% SiC_p (1.9 μm) sample was studied using SEM at 500 and 2500 magnification. The micrographs were used to analyze the volume fraction of the micro constituents. The calculations were done by tracing the microstructure on a graph sheet and then estimating the area fraction occupied by each of these constituents. The microstructure and the tracing at lower magnification are shown in Fig.5a and b respectively. The same at higher magnification are shown in Fig.6a and b. The microstructure of Al alloy / 30 vol.% SiC_p

Fig.4. Microstructures of Al alloy matrix composite with a) 15 vol% SiC (14μm) b) 15 vol% SiC (1.9μm) and c) 30 vol% SiC (1.9μm).

Fig.5 Al alloy / 30 vol% SiC_p composite (500X): a) SEM micrograph and b) Its tracing used for area fraction calculation.

composite consists of necklace type structure around matrix Al particles. The necklace itself is another composite having higher volume fraction of SiC_p. From Fig.5b it is clear that the area fraction of matrix (called M) is about 44.6% and that of the necklace (called N is 55.4%). From Fig.6b at high magnification it was found that the necklace region consists of 50% SiC_p (called R) and 50% aluminium alloy matrix (called NM). Therefore in a composite the plain matrix (M) is 44.6%, the reinforcement(R) is 27.8% and the matrix within necklace is 27.6%.

$$C = 44.6\% M + 55.4\% N = 44.6\% M + 27.8\% R + 27.6\% NM$$

Fig.6 Al alloy/ 30 vol % SiC (2500 X): a) SEM micrograph and b) Its tracing used for area fraction calculations.

It was also observed that the size of the capillaries in between SiC_p particles in the necklace region is about 1-2 μm . Most of the Al matrix (NM) present in between the necklace region has to infiltrate through the capillaries. The penetration is possible only by liquid phase and not by solid phase. Hence, at the temperature of pressing the material should contain adequate liquid phase to completely infiltrate the capillaries in between SiC_p . From the back scattered images of Al alloy/ SiC_p composite shown in Fig. 7, it can be observed that most of the matrix present in between SiC particles is rich in Cu and Mg and the same is infiltrated into the capillaries. Based on these observations and calculations the probable mechanism of hot pressing may be proposed to consist of four stages as explained below.

Stage I : During cold / pre solidus compaction matrix particles get consolidated, by pushing SiC particles present around their surface, to maximum possible densification of SiC at the applied load. If full densification of Al powder is assumed, as per the compaction curve of SiC in Fig.10 at 115 MPa load the maximum densification of 1.9 μm size SiC is about 85%.

Stage II : The 15% porosity present in the vicinity of the SiC particulates is to be filled up by infiltration of liquid phase that forms while raising the temperature. The applied load must be adequate to cause infiltration of liquid metal into capillaries.

Stage III : Due to poor wettability of SiC with Al alloy, initially the liquid metal that gets infiltrated into the capillaries, pushes SiC. Hence the SiC particles get pushed away slightly and this results in the increased gap between SiC particles due to which the matrix region in the network was found to be 28 % against the porosity in between SiC particles i.e., 15%.

Stage IV : When the external pressure is removed at the end of pressing cycle, the liquid metal present in between SiC particles won't flow out of capillaries due to : a) improved wetting with increased contact time and b) resistance offered by the capillary forces to the flow of liquid.

Fig.7. Back scattered electron images of Al alloy composite with SiC_p (1.9 μm) a) 15 vol% and b) 30 vol%

Fig.8. Compaction curve for 1.9 μm SiC_p

Fig.9. Porosity in MMC with 30 vol% SiC.

The network volume and the size of capillaries depend upon the volume fraction of reinforcement and its particle size, whereas compaction pressure has only a marginal effect on the capillary size as can be seen from Fig. 8. Therefore the amount of liquid phase i.e., processing temperature has to be decided based on volume fraction and particle size of the reinforcement, whereas applied pressure should be adequate to cause infiltration of liquid metal through the capillaries. In general as volume fraction increases and liquid metal has to penetrate longer distances hence pressure should be high. As the network volume increases, more liquid phase is required hence the temperature also should be high. As the particle size decreases the capillary size decreases. Hence more pressure is required to push the liquid metal into capillaries. The microstructure given in Fig. 9. highlights the presence of porosity at the centre of network as a result of inadequate liquid content due to lower processing temperature.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Atomised Al - 4.0 Cu - 1.5 Mg alloy powder of less than 200 # was blended with 0, 15 and 30 vol.% of SiC_p of 1.9 µm and 14 µm size and vacuum hot pressed into fully dense billets. The influence of compacting pressure and temperature on the consolidation behaviour of these composites was investigated. The compaction curves were generated for these materials as a function of compacting pressure in I stage compaction and as a function of temperature in II stage compaction.

SEM microstructure of the composite shows a necklace type structure. By analyzing the microstructure of Al/30 vol% SiC it was proposed that about 28% of liquid metal gets infiltrated into the SiC_p network to complete the full densification. A four stage densification mechanism has been proposed to explain the compaction behaviour of composites during hot pressing.

As the SiC_p volume fraction increases, the width and volume of necklace region increases thereby necessitating higher hot pressing temperature and pressure. As SiC_p particle size decreases the capillary size in the necklace region decreases and demands higher pressure. However further investigation is required in terms of quantification of these effects and validation of the mechanism by correlation of the observation using phase diagram. Efforts are now being concentrated by the authors to explain this mechanism in detail.

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